

Sorption and Desorption of Crystal Violet and Malachite Green on and from Vermiculite

D. K. DE*, J. L. DAS KANUNGO and S. K. CHAKRAVARTI

Department of Chemistry, University of North Bengal, P. O. North Bengal University,
Dist. Darjeeling, W. Bengal.

Manuscript received 21 March 1978, revised 30 August 1978, accepted 24 April 1979

Adsorption and desorption studies of crystal violet (CV) and malachite green (MG) have been carried on and from Vermiculite. Of the two dyes the sorption data of crystal violet alone obey the Langmuir equation. The release of the dye ions from their respective clay matrixes by different ions follows the order: $\text{Na} < \text{NH}_4 < \text{K} < \text{H} < \text{Mg} < \text{Ca} < \text{Ba}$ for crystal violet and $\text{Na} < \text{NH}_4 < \text{K} < \text{H} < \text{Ca} < \text{Ba} < \text{Mg}$ for malachite green. The order of the relative binding strength of the dyes for the vermiculite surface, which is in the reverse order of their desorption is: $\text{CV} > \text{MG}$. From the sorption data the specific surface area of the mineral has been calculated and the possible modes of orientation of the dye molecules on to the surface have been suggested.

THE sorption of cationic dyes on clay minerals although taking place primarily through ion exchange reaction^{1,2} is so complicated with a number of peculiarities^{3,4} that it can hardly be generalised for other organic cations⁵. Nonetheless adsorption isotherms of dyes⁶ can give useful information about the identification of the adsorption mechanism, diagnosis of the orientation of the solute molecules at the surface and the specific surface area of finely divided or porous solids. On the other hand, the desorption studies of the dyes by different ions is going to show the extent of extractibility of these dyes from the mineral surface from which we can have an idea of the affinity of the dyes for the mineral surface as well as of the relative desorbing abilities of the ions. In view of the above a systematic attempt has been made in this paper to study the adsorption behaviour of two cationic dyes namely crystal violet and malachite green on the Vermiculite and their desorption against various inorganic ions.

Experimental

Clay fractions having particle size $< 2.0\mu$ were isolated and collected by the usual method of dispersion and sedimentation. Vermiculite from the Geological Survey of India, Calcutta, was used and judged to be pure Vermiculite by us from X-ray diffraction studies. The cation exchange capacity (cec) of H-Vermiculite was found to be 133.0 me/100 g by titration with baryta in presence of molar BaCl_2 solution using phenolphthalein as indicator. For adsorption experiments 10 ml portions of 0.78% H-clay suspension were taken in different stoppered pyrex bottles and dye solutions of known concentration were added in increasing amounts. The total volumes were adjusted to 20 ml by adding requisite amounts of water. The bottles, with their contents, were shaken for one hour and kept overnight for equilibration. Next day the bottles were shaken for one hour and the mixtures were centrifuged for 30

minutes or so, and the supernatant liquids were analysed colorimetrically in the spekkar (Hilger) using proper filters. From the difference between the initial concentration and that of the equilibrium concentration, measured above, the amount adsorbed was determined.

For the purpose of desorption studies the H-Vermiculite suspensions were mixed with dye solution containing about one and half times the predetermined cec of the clay, shaken for one hour and allowed to equilibrate overnight as before. The excess dye was then washed several times with distilled water till the leachate gave constant optical density. The suspension of the clay-dye complex in water was used for desorption experiments. The percentages of the clay-dye complexes were 0.25 for CV and 0.77 for MG. For investigating the desorption of the dyes from the clay matrix, 10 ml aliquots of the suspension were taken in stoppered pyrex test tubes to which increasing amounts of different electrolytes were added. The total volume was adjusted with water to 12 ml in all the cases. The test tubes with their contents were shaken for fifteen minutes and kept overnight. The minerals were then centrifuged for thirty minutes or so and the dye contents of the clear centrifugates were measured as described earlier. Crystal violet and Malachite green were of E. Merck quality and were used as such without further purification.

Results and Discussion

The adsorption isotherms of CV and MG are shown in Figs. 1 & 2. $\frac{C}{x}$ vs C , where C is the equilibrium concentration of the dye and x is the amount adsorbed per 100g of adsorbent, plot (Figs. 1b & 2b) yields a good straight line for CV and a curvature is noticed with MG. These indicate that the sorption data of CV on

* Present address : R.B.C. College, Naihati, W. Bengal.

Fig. 1. Adsorption isotherm (a) and Langmuir plot of CV (b) on H-Vermiculite.

Fig. 2. Adsorption isotherm (a) and Langmuir plot of MG (b) on H-Vermiculite.

H-Vermiculite fit in with the Langmuir equation, although the case is somewhat different for MG. It is likely that the condition of Langmuir type isotherm, i.e. strong interaction between the adsorbate and the adsorbent is not fully satisfied in the latter case. The CV molecule has three positive nitrogen sites and MG molecule has two such sites by resonance. The rather unusual sluggish isotherm observed in the case of MG is possibly a combined effect of the weak affinity of the dye due to smaller number of charge centres and limited C-axis expansion of Vermiculite. The structure of Vermiculite⁷ consists of sheets of tri-octahedral mica or talc stacked one above the other in the C-axis direction separated by layers of water molecules occupying a definite space (4.98Å) and having a net charge deficiency which is balanced by hydrated magnesium ions occurring between the silicate layers. These structural characteristics prevent the expansion of the mineral in the C-axis dimension, when treated with polar molecules.

According to Giles et al⁶ L-curves or Langmuir isotherms, usually indicative of molecules adsorbed flat

on the surface. However, other orientations such as edge-on or end-on are not entirely ruled out. Assuming a flat orientation of CV molecules (coverage area 171 Å² in hydrated condition⁸) on to the mineral, the specific surface area of the Vermiculite has been calculated to be 743 m²/g. The coverage area per MG molecule with reference to this surface area is 113.4 Å², which is a little higher than 110 Å², the calculated area of MG molecule in flat position. This indicates that the MG molecules are predominantly anchored flat to the clay surface.

The influence of the size of the dye ions is shown up more explicitly in the case of vermiculite than montmorillonite. The latter swells considerably so that the sizes of the adsorbate ions assume less importance, whereas in vermiculite the interlamellar space is limited to the thickness of about two water molecules⁷ (4.98Å) and hence the influence of the size becomes more pronounced here. According to their sizes the dye ions arrange as MG < CV and hence the adsorption of the dyes varies in the reverse order. It is also observed that the amount of dyes sorbed corresponding to the maximum of the isotherms (27 me/100g for CV and 36.2 me/100g for MG) is much less than the cec of Vermiculite (133.0 me/100g). As pointed out earlier it is quite likely that the interlamellar space of vermiculite, which unlike montmorillonite, is non-expandable⁷ is not fully accessible to these large dye ions. Moreover, it is also possible that the initially sorbed dyes prevent, in a physical sense, entry of further dye ions into the interior of the interlamellar space.

The desorption isotherms of CV and MG from their respective vermiculite complexes are shown in Figs. 3 & 4. The distribution and selectivity coefficients were calculated from the desorption data corresponding to a definite concentration of the desorbing electrolyte and are recorded in table 1.

Assuming the ion exchange equilibrium⁹ as

Fig. 3. Desorption of CV from CV-Vermiculite by different ions.

Fig. 4. Desorption of MG from MG-Vermiculite by different ions.

where D stands for the dye, the bar denotes the species in the clay phase and Z is the valency of the ion, the selectivity coefficients were calculated according to the equation⁹.

$$k_D = \frac{[D][i^{+z}]^{1/z}}{[\bar{D}][i^{+z}]^{1/z}}$$

The distribution coefficients are given by $\lambda_i = \frac{\bar{m}_i}{m_i}$, where \bar{m}_i and m_i are the molar concentrations of the species *i* in the clay and solution phases respectively.

From Fig. 3 it may be observed that the desorption curves of CV are almost linear with all the monovalent

TABLE 1—DESORPTION CHARACTERISTICS OF CV AND MG BY DIFFERENT IONS FROM THEIR RESPECTIVE VERMICULITE COMPLEXES

Electrolyte used	Concentration of electrolyte (M)	Distribution coefficient		Selectivity coefficient	
		CV	MG	CV	MG
1 : 1 electrolyte					
NaCl	1.1×10^{-2}	0.16	1.42	0.23×10^{-5}	0.41×10^{-4}
NH ₄ Cl	„	0.25	2.41	0.53×10^{-5}	1.22×10^{-4}
KCl	„	0.27	2.47	0.62×10^{-5}	1.28×10^{-4}
HCl	„	0.39	2.80	0.82×10^{-5}	1.50×10^{-4}
2 : 1 electrolyte					
MgCl ₂	„	0.65	3.85	4.50×10^{-5}	1.66×10^{-4}
CaCl ₂	„	0.68	3.68	4.85×10^{-5}	1.54×10^{-4}
BaCl ₂	„	0.70	3.83	5.08×10^{-5}	1.64×10^{-4}

ions over the concentrations used, but are slightly curved for the bivalent ions. The linearity is probably the consequence of a weak exchanging power of the monovalent ions. The desorption curves of MG however, exhibit usual behaviour although the selectivity reversal of Mg⁺⁺ and Ba⁺⁺ at higher concentrations are noticed (Fig. 4). On the basis of the distribution and selectivity coefficients the order of release of the dye ions from their respective clay matrixes is : Na < NH₄ < K < H < Mg < Ca < Ba for CV and Na < NH₄ < K < H < Ca < Ba < Mg for MG. The variable position of the bivalent ions in the series is to be noted. Such deviation has also been observed by other workers^{10,11} and has been ascribed to change in hydration relative to other bivalent cations and by their closer approach to the silicate surfaces. The anomalous position of H⁺ in the series is well known^{12,13} and the idea of the bare proton taking part in the exchange reactions may be invoked to explain the peculiar behaviour of H⁺.

Table 1 makes it apparent that the values of the selectivity coefficients of the desorbing cations are higher with MG than CV. Hence the order of the relative binding strength of the dyes for the vermiculite surface, which is in the reverse order of their desorption is CV > MG. As pointed out earlier, this is also expected from the resonance structures of the dyes which locate three possible charge centres for CV and two for MG. Therefore, CV is likely to have greater affinity for the mineral surface.

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